

‘INFLUENCING WITHOUT POWER’ FOR A GOOD CAUSE - THE EXPERIENCE OF GAZA RESILIENCE LAB

Mohamed Buheji

Founder, Socioeconomic Institute for Advanced Studies (SIAS), Rwanda

ABSTRACT

The 2023/2024 War on Gaza, despite its many challenges, has illuminated unique opportunities for the Free-Palestine cause, particularly the potential for influence without formal power. This paper explores the emergence of 'live models' who have exemplified resilience and ingenuity in breaking the blockade around Gaza, inspiring individuals and communities all over the world to engage and contribute meaningfully.

This paper explores how influence can be cultivated with soft power through storytelling, community engagement, and leveraging fundamental human values. Sharing experiences and challenges relevant to the War on Gaza can create ripple effects, motivating others and strengthening grassroots movements. The war has also underscored the importance of empowering community members through building cross-generational connections and social media advocacy, so that they can act as ambassadors for the Palestinian Cause even beyond the war on Gaza 2023/2024.

The researcher examines how Gaza's resilience lab supports creating waves of 'influence without power', through basic formulas that bring simple solutions for Gaza's basic needs that are even alarming with the limitation of health services, and infrastructure destruction, besides the socio-political and socioeconomic challenges. The formulas guide impactful change and foster a more profound, sustained support for Gaza and the broader Free-Palestine movement.

Keywords: Influencing Without Power, Gaza Resilience Lab, War on Gaza, Palestine.

Cite this Article: Mohamed Buheji, ‘Influencing Without Power’ for A Good Cause - The Experience of Gaza Resilience Lab, International Journal of Social Sciences Research and Development (IJSSRD), 6(2), 2024, pp. 1-12.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12703095>

https://iaeme.com/MasterAdmin/Journal_uploads/IJSSRD/VOLUME_6_ISSUE_2/IJSSRD_06_02_001.pdf

1. INTRODUCTION

The Cause of Free-Palestine and the War on Gaza 2023/2024, brought opportunities from many challenges. One of the main opportunities is the need to create an influence without power to put more pressure on the Western nations to take a better stand for Palestine and the Palestinian needs. People, especially in the Islamic world, are looking for (live models) who have managed to break the chain around Gaza during the war of 2023/02024, which can inspire others to get involved and contribute their efforts. However, the real inspiration is within each of us, and each can write a narrative about his/her role in creating change despite the challenges and restrictions. It is all about how we effectively bring people together for collaborative initiatives. And in this paper, we illustrate live models of how we managed to unite diverse stakeholders under a common cause that can drive impactful change.

The argument here is that each person can create a positive influence towards Gaza through sharing experiences with peers that can create a ripple effect of engagement, and then using storytelling to humanize the experiences of (live models). Sharing personal journeys and challenges faced along the way can resonate with others and motivate action.

The war on Gaza has also brought many opportunities to return to basic human values, build cross-generational connections, and facilitate interactions between community members from different generations. Suppose community members are empowered with the mindset to act as ambassadors on social media platforms for the Palestinian Cause, sharing their own experiences, and insights. In that case, this might lead to another chain of influence without the need for power, or resources.

The literature review introduces the 'Theory of Influence without Power,' highlighting its components and the role of inspiration economy tools in effecting change. This theory is pivotal in understanding how influence can be harnessed through intrinsic community strengths and non-traditional economies like knowledge, creativity, and resilience. We outline the criteria for influence to occur without authority, focusing on capacity, relationships, and clarity of purpose.

The paper further examines how Gaza's resilience can be supported through influence without power, from addressing basic needs and health services to infrastructure reconstruction and socio-political challenges. The formula's developed by the author propose strategies for building rapport, credibility, and emotional connections, emphasizing the role of reciprocity and social proof in sustaining support for Gaza.

The paper illustrates how diverse stakeholders can unite under a common cause through case studies and theoretical frameworks, driving impactful change and fostering a more profound, sustained support for Gaza and the broader Free-Palestine movement.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Defining Influence and its Sources

Influence is about raising the capacity to help shape what happens next and the ability to affect the behaviour of others, which would increase the quality of the impact, relevance to the communicated content, and the targeted audience. Thus, new actions, behaviors, and opinions are produced in the targeted direction. Buheji (2016)

We can improve the network through influence, raise credibility and trustworthiness, bring in open and flexible solutions, and make people speak up about complicated situations. Some influence can be through comparison, giving something away, sacrificing, or creating examples. For influence to occur, common points must be planned to reflect logic and emotions. The outcome of influence is usually higher commitment, better compliance and more resistance or resilience.

2.2. Introduction ‘Theory of Influence without Power’ as per Inspiration Economy

The author introduced the theory of ‘influencing without power’ as part of the inspiration economy (IE) tools and mechanisms to raise the ability to evaluate the targeted change and desired effect through indirect influence, seeing challenges as opportunities for differentiation (including determining the nature of the challenges that hinder the implementation of the impact in an integrated manner). The theory is based on measuring performance with impact levels and with a renewed view (including speed of response in cases of societal imbalance, explanation, learning and deduction for the causes of the defect and preventing its recurrence). Buheji (2016)

The theory is unique in its ability to create inspiring currency without authority or without dependence on extrinsic resources. IE uses (non-classical economies) as knowledge, creativity, resilience, youth, future foresight economies could be used as tools to create this influence without authority or power that leads to more inspiration currency. As a theory, influencing without power takes advantage of the power of (positive feedback) to create competitive and coexisting communities. Buheji (2021)

2.2. Criteria for Influence to Occur without Authority

Analysing the theory of ‘influencing without power’ requires three basic elements that be available to influence or occur, or sustain, without the need for extra resources or high power or authority; these are: the focus on the capacity, the benefits from the relationships, the clarity in the target idea. The impact of this influence means having the ability to make others voluntarily do what is desired. The other ingredients for ‘influence without power’ theories can be related to the type of relationship network, the conviction and constructive feedback and the consultations from the public and the beneficiaries at the right time and environment. ‘Influencing without power’ as a theory brings in many types of hidden or under-utilised powers within the community, such as the power of diversity, the strength of observation, the logic of intuitions and willpower.

2.3. Helping Gaza through Influencing without Power

After hostilities cease in regions like Gaza, many challenges often emerge, reflecting the complex interplay of humanitarian, socioeconomic, and political factors. Most of the sympathisers think they can only help Gaza with relevance to humanitarian challenges, especially if the borders are open or by trying to help the displaced and homeless during or after the war on Gaza by different limited means. These challenges can bring a source of depression, feelings of letdown, or loss of hope to both the people of Gaza and the sympathisers with Gaza and the Palestinian Cause in genera. However, this should not be the case if we see that challenges should be a source of inspiration if we realise the formula that works on raising the (Capacity vs. Demand), Buheji (2016). For the last part, i.e. the War on Gaza being a source of inspiration is a type of currency, if well utilised along with the mindset that knows how to ‘influence without the dependency on power’ (be it governments, money, celebrity position, etc.) it can bring in best relief to sympathisers.

2.4. Difference of ‘Influencing without Power’ (IWF) Model

IWF help to go toward the present vision and solve problems through available resources, which creates further human motivations. With IWF we can manage conflicting views by finding compromises and do the right things followed by doing things right.

To create a flexible mindset that believes in our ability to “influence without power,” we need to do activities that trigger the involvement of the Reticular Activating System (RAS) area in our brain. RAS is considered to be the gatekeeper between the conscious and unconscious parts of the mind. Through selecting what RAS should focus on, we can visualise our ability to reach our life-purposefulness goals. Then, all the efforts will mainly be analysed from this point. So, once our brains become responsive to RAS, we will explore more undiscovered opportunities. Buheji (2016)

Influence without formal power can be a powerful tool for driving positive change in your community's fight against poverty. By building relationships, sharing knowledge, fostering collaboration, and inspiring collective action, we can make a meaningful impact and contribute to a brighter future for those in need. However, this needs the following pre-requisites realizing the situation, mapping the social assets, choosing influence tactics and desired outcomes, and identifying or modifying “vital behaviors”.

Using influence without formal power to address poverty and mobilize a community requires a strategic approach that builds relationships, credibility, and a shared vision for change. Thus, IWP requires genuine connections with community members, leaders, and stakeholders. Listen to their concerns, understand their needs, and show empathy for their experiences. Buheji (2020) saw that IWP helps to engage in collaborative dialogue that initiates conversations and open dialogues about poverty within the community.

2.5. Exploring the type of influences that could help to sustain the Profound Support for Gaza

Creating value-based profound support can help build experiences through field, academic and disruptive approaches (none-traditional sense). These values are transmitted through showing the role of the religion and the culture. This can be emphasized by giving further support to citizen journalism to provide real-time updates and personal perspectives from people on the ground in Gaza.

Sustaining profound support for Gaza involves leveraging various types of influences that can engage and mobilize different sectors of society, from grassroots activists to international policymakers. Therefore, Pro-Gaza symthisers should ensure consistent and accurate coverage of the situation in Gaza through newspapers, television, and radio to keep the issue in the public eye. They should work on producing and promoting documentaries and films that highlight personal stories, historical context, and current challenges the people in Gaza face. Besides, utilizing platforms like Twitter, Facebook, Instagram, and YouTube to raise awareness, share stories, and mobilize support through hashtags, viral content, and influencer collaborations.

Part of the sources of influence towards Gaza is to organize art exhibitions featuring works by Palestinian artists that depict life in Gaza and the impact of the conflict. Books, poems, and essays by writers from or about Gaza can also be promoted to provide deeper insights into the experiences and resilience of its people.

To create further influence, well-known artists and musicians need to be engaged to create works that highlight the plight of Gaza and inspire action. Besides, hosting benefit concerts, theater performances, and cultural events that draw attention to the situation in Gaza and raise funds for humanitarian efforts.

The other type of influence without power is the support that can come from academic research that investigates the social, economic, and political conditions in Gaza, which leads to publishing findings in peer-reviewed journals and platforms. Public lectures, panel discussions, and seminars featuring experts on Gaza must be encouraged to educate the public and policymakers.

More than ever, part of the influence needed is the need to develop educational materials and programs for schools that include the history and current issues of Gaza, fostering a more informed and empathetic younger generation. If this is available, then it is worth introducing courses at universities focusing on Palestine and Palestinian rights along with the Middle Eastern studies, conflict resolution, or humanitarian aid, with specific modules on Gaza.

Regardless of one speciality, we can also partner with NGOs to run advocacy campaigns that highlight the needs of Gaza and call for international support. These NGOs should be supported to provide essential services such as healthcare, education, and food security in Gaza.

Furthermore, grassroots movements such as those engaging local communities in advocacy and support efforts, rallies, petition drives, and awareness campaigns should be encouraged. This would create further opportunities for volunteers to contribute to humanitarian projects and advocacy efforts focused on Gaza. Local businesses should be encouraged to adopt social responsibility initiatives supporting Gaza through donations, sponsorships, and NGO partnerships. Most importantly, the influence should focus on Gaza's independence, which promotes and supports businesses and entrepreneurs in Gaza to stimulate the local economy and provide sustainable livelihoods.

3. METHODOLOGY

This paper optimizes the literature review to bring in the type of influences that can be possible, needed and has been done through the case of Gaza Resilience Lab. The methodology helps to build an example of how influence ripple effect can start with simple efforts, but would lead to great impact as it meets other variables. The author uses simple formulas to illustrate the type of influence achieved by connecting different constructs or tools of soft change power.

The author proposes a framework for creating and maintaining such momentum by others, taking the Gaza Resilience Lab as an example only.

4. APPLICATION & ANALYSIS OF INFLUENCES WITH POWER ON GAZA RESILIENCE

In reference to the literature review and the drive to change the mindset about the reality of the Israeli Occupation in Palestine, one can refer to the work of *Lauren Keller Johnson*

() *“Tactics for Changing Minds” focuses on creating influence through optimizing the following seven variables (7 R’s): reason, research, resonance, repetition, resources and rewards, real-world events and resistance. These 7R’s can be engulfed inside each one or all of the following influencing sources without power.*

4.1. Influences on Access to Basic Needs

Ensuring access to basic needs such as food, clean water, and healthcare became a significant challenge because all these infrastructures have been intentionally targeted and damaged. These basic life needs cannot be addressed easily with the sustained atrocities of the Israel Defence Forces (IDF). However, they can be mitigated by other means that ease the impact on the people of Gaza and the pro-Palestine advocates.

One of the basic influences is to support Gazans to see the variety of ‘Reasons to Live’; and be steadfast to the Cause especially after they have lost many of their loved ones and almost all the sources of life and maybe the possible future quality of life. Buheji and Mushimiyanama (2024b) called for an assessment of current scenarios and foresighted future.

To support Gaza’s resilience Buheji and Khunji (2023) called for rehabilitating its wellbeing through storytelling (during and after the war 2023/2024) that would help in dealing with loss-coping with the yearning for lost livelihood, Buheji (2004d). Shorrab et al. (2024) called for the analysis and mitigation of the health risks of the 2023 war on Gaza to support the basic needs of life. Hassoun et al. (2024) pointed out that the acute food insecurity would lead to famine and dramatically would set back any possible sustainable development goals in Gaza. Therefore, Buheji (2024a) sees that we need to consider ‘collective pain’ and ‘collective happiness’ in Gaza to overcome the possibilities of ‘resilience fatigue’.

4.2. Influence on the Accessibility to Physical and Mental Health Services

Beyond immediate injuries, there's a need for psychological support for trauma, as well as rehabilitation services for those injured, besides overcoming the feelings of betrayal and let down, which might lead to both famine and chaos in Gaza, Buheji (2024f). To overcome the impact of this situation, Buheji (2024b) called for addressing human factors in Gaza, foresighting future challenges and solutions for post-war recovery.

4.3. Influence on Infrastructure Reconstruction Needs

Rebuilding essential infrastructure, such as roads, schools, hospitals, and utilities, is a significant task that would help restore livelihoods and economic structures, including markets and businesses, is crucial for the long-term stability of Gaza. Besides addressing environmental damages such as unexploded ordnance and rubble removal, it is necessary for safety and health. Therefore, Buheji and Al-Muhannadi (2023) called for mitigating the risks of environmental impacts on Gaza by reviewing precautions and solutions post (2023/2024 War).

4.4. Influence on Sociopolitical Challenges

In order to create influence without power on the sociopolitical challenges, we need to foster a sense of community and address grievances that may have been exacerbated by the conflict so that we can establish effective governance and legal frameworks to ensure security, justice, and human rights in Gaza. This would include addressing the resilience mechanisms that need to be exemplified by the Palestinians in Gaza during the negotiations with the IDF. Therefore, Buheji and Mushimiyimana (2023b) focused on raising Gaza ‘survival capacity’ as per the type of violence experienced, using lessons from the the best war survival stories in recent history. They believed this would raise Gaza towards an ‘agile resilience’ level. Buheji and Mushimiyimana (2023a).

Al-Muhannadi and Buheji (2024) see that to support overcoming the sociopolitical demands, Gazan must focus on sustain delivering value-based resilience stories capitalising on the rising support and the limited accessibility of social media. This would help overcome the collective punish, ethnic cleansing and deliberate genocide efforts. Hasan and Buheji (2024)

This persistence of the Palestinians not to flee Gaza also played a great role in gaining support from different European countries such as Spain, Ireland, Belgium, Brussels, and Norway which led to their recognition of the Palestinian state. Actually, Buheji and Hasan (2024c) called the world to study further the model ‘Spain's Empathy for Gaza’ as a model for the sociopolitical balance between the government and its community's demands. They have further seen that capitalising on the ‘social capital’ of Gaza would accelerate its collective wealth, especially the sociopolitical one, Buheji and Hasan (2024c). This would build a rapport between the dissolved South African apartheid and the apartheid developed by the Israeli occupation in Palestine. Buheji and Hasan (2024e)

4.5. Influence on Economic Challenges Transitions

Rebuilding the economy and providing employment opportunities in Gaza, especially for the youth, is critical to prevent despair and instability. This would include transitioning from emergency aid to sustainable development to ensure long-term economic stability. Therefore, Buheji and Hamza (2024) called for working on Gaza branding as a brand of resilience so that Gaza's global identity can be a narrative source of solidarity, and advocacy besides generating an income for its people.

4.6. Influence on Educational and Cultural Means

The question here is how we can influence ensuring children won't lose school and prevent losing a generation without education. How can we eliminate the impact of the lost cultural heritage sites even though the IDF has damaged them. For the first one Buheji and Buheji (2024) called for mitigating risks of slow children development due to war on Gaza. Phusavat and Buheji (2024) seen that this can be done by mapping informal learning for displaced learners during the war and the application of 'situated cognition'. Therefore, Hasan (2024) has gone to show the history of the Palestinian education system and its resilience under the occupation. Both Buheji and Hasan showed that this resilience moved many pro-Palestine protests from students worldwide and made them sacrifice further to change this type of oppression. Even the authors called for challenging this educate injustice by stretching the 'Academic Boycott' even further after the war on Gaza 2023/2024 ends. Buheji et al. (2024a) and Buheji and Hasan (2024b).

4.7. Influencing through Reciprocity

Reciprocity means (give and take) between you and others, enabling you to change or reinforce their attitudes, opinions, or behaviours (Cohen and Bradford (2005). Through reciprocity, we can raise the capacity to shape what happens next. Producing effects on the actions, behaviour or opinion of others. To raise the flow of reciprocity, Buheji et al. (2024b) called for empathic engagement with Gaza by managing the dynamics, impact, and prospects of empathy, as a result, Buheji and Ahmed (2024a) managed to set a profound scale that bring insights from testing empathy levels towards Gaza. Buheji (2024e) seen that this empathy exemplifies more with Gen-Z who are changing further the mindset of the world about the truth of Israeli Occupation through connecting the dots and re-establishing the true story of Palestine.

Part of the reciprocity with Gaza's inspiration is to keep on the boycott momentum- from 'war on Gaza' till 'Free-Palestine', Buheji and Ahmed (2023). This can be more supported by the echoes of wake-up-realising the impact of the Pro-Palestine students' protests, Buheji and Hasan (2024c). Furthermore, Buheji and Hasan (2024a) called for optimising celebrities engagement and reaction on the situation of Gaza.

5. KEY FORMULAS THAT HELP TO CREATE 'INFLUENCE WITHOUT POWER' TOWARDS GAZA SURVIVAL AND FREE-PALESTINE

Linda Hill (1994) mentioned in her book on "Exercising Influence" that we can create the power of influence by empowering others to cultivate networks that become part of the resistance to the occupation.

As mentioned earlier, the idea of ‘influencing without power’ involves leveraging various psychological and social strategies to persuade and guide others without relying on formal authority or coercive means. The main constructs of these formulas are the rapport network, the mutual benefits, the reciprocity, the values and the emotions shared, use of the social proof, and compromising solutions.

5.1. Formula for Effective Participation and Communication

To get people involved with Gaza and the Palestinian Cause, a sense of ownership and responsibility for the outcomes must be encouraged. This can happen through the first formula that ensures effective communication based on clear, concise, persuasive language and techniques, besides messages tailored to the audience’s needs and preferences.

$$\{Effective\ Communication\} = \{Clarity\} + \{Persuasion\} + \{Adaptation\}$$

$$\{Participation\} = \{Involvement\} + \{Ownership\}$$

5.2. Formula for Building Rapport for Gaza

To build proper rapport in Gaza, we need to focus on empathy, which helps show a genuine understanding of Gazans' feelings and perspectives, besides paying full attention to common grounds and shared values. To spread mutual benefit for Gaza and Palestine's Freedom creating, we need to align interests and identify overlapping goals. Therefore, the formula proposed for building rapport between Gaza and then Palestine is:

$$\{Rapport\ \&\ Mutual\ Benefit\} = \{Empathy\} + \{Active\ Listening\} + \{Common\ Ground\}$$

5.3. Formula for Raising the Reciprocity Flow for Gaza

Reciprocity is important for strengthening the rapport. Gazans have given the world a new level of resilience and values during times of conflict, and part of appreciating their role in the world awakening is to give them support and help. This would create a sense of obligation or indebtedness towards each other.

$$\{Reciprocity\} = \{Giving\ First\} + \{Creating\ Obligation\}$$

5.4. Formula for Building Credibility

Suppose rapport and reciprocity are built in relation to Gaza and the Palestinian Cause in general. In that case, we can build credibility towards the voices coming from inside the occupied lands since they demonstrate knowledge and competence in the relevant area, besides being trusted to be honest, reliable, and consistent.

$$\{Credibility\} = \{Expertise\} + \{Trustworthiness\}$$

5.5. Formula for Appealing to Values and Emotions

Emotional connections can result from connecting with Gazans where the emotional level, sharing the stories and experiences would be at its best. At this stage, core values and deep beliefs could be aligned.

$$\{Emotional\ Appeal\} = \{Emotional\ Connection\} + \{Value\ Alignment\}$$

5.6. Formula for Optimising the Social Proof

Using testimonials or endorsements from respected individuals can help highlight how peers or similar individuals engage in desired behaviours.

$$\{Social\ Proof\} = \{Endorsements\} + \{Peer\ Influence\}$$

5.7. Formula for Effective Compromising

Compromise in certain areas and aspects is part of the long struggle towards free Palestine, but it needs high resilience and willingness to adapt and find a middle ground during different journey stages. This means that to create influence, we need to be opportunities-focused rather than solution-focused. i.e. Focused on finding mutually acceptable solutions that bring new opportunities for the freedom journey.

$$\{Effective\ Approach\} \quad \{Compromising\} = \{Preparation\} + \{Flexibility\} + \{Solution-Focused\}$$

6. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The 2023/2024 War on Gaza has brought to light the profound potential for creating significant change through ‘influencing without power’ or formal power. This approach, rooted in the principles of the inspiration economy, demonstrates that true power lies within the collective strength and resilience of individuals and communities. The concept of 'live models' offers a tangible source of inspiration, showcasing how ordinary people can break barriers and instigate change even in the most challenging circumstances, similar to the situation in Gaza during the Israeli aggression.

The author's exploration reveals that influence can be effectively harnessed through storytelling, community engagement, and the strategic use of social media. These tools enable individuals to share their experiences and challenges, creating a ripple effect that fosters widespread engagement and support. The emphasis on cross-generational connections and basic human values has proven essential in building a strong, united front for the Palestinian Cause.

The 'Theory of Influence without Power' provides a robust framework for understanding how change can be achieved through intrinsic strengths and non-traditional economic resources. By focusing on capacity, relationships, and clarity of purpose, communities can drive impactful change without relying on traditional power structures or resources. The paper has highlighted several strategies for supporting Gaza's resilience, from meeting basic needs and providing health services to rebuilding infrastructure and addressing socio-political challenges. These strategies underscore the importance of empathy, reciprocity, and the power of shared narratives in sustaining long-term support.

In conclusion, the fight for Gaza and the broader Free-Palestine movement can be significantly advanced through the collective efforts of individuals and communities. By leveraging the power of influence without formal authority, we can create a more just and supportive environment for Gaza, fostering hope and resilience amidst adversity. The lessons learned from this approach offer valuable insights for other movements seeking to drive change in similarly challenging contexts. Figure (1) proposes that influencing without power is a must when risk vs. complexity is high over time, otherwise resistance movements and those working for radical change, such as the Free-Palestine movement, would end up dissipating their energy while waiting for power.

Figure (1) Importance of Influencing without Power when Risks & Complexity is high

REFERENCES

- [1] Allan R. Cohen and David L. Bradford, (2005) *Influence Without Authority*, 2nd Edition
- [2] Al-Muhannadi, K and Buheji, M (2024) Value-Based Resilience Stories from Gaza (During War 2023), *International Journal of Management (IJM)*, 15(1), pp. 15-37.
- [3] Buheji, M (2024a) Avoiding Resilience Fatigue- Navigating ‘Collective Pain’ and ‘Collective Happiness’ in Gaza (War of 2023/2024), *International Journal of Psychology and Behavioral Sciences* 2024, 14(1): 22-33.
- [4] Buheji, M (2024b) Addressing Human Factors in Gaza: Challenges and Solutions for Post-War Recovery, *International Journal of Management (IJM)*, 15(3), pp. 35-45.
- [5] Buheji, M (2024c) Connecting The Dotts.. How Gen-Z Re-Establishing the True Story of Palestine? *International Journal of Social Sciences Research and Development (IJSSRD)*, 6(1), 2024, pp. 179-199.
- [6] Buheji, M (2004d) Dealing with Loss -Coping with Yearning of Lost Livelihood - Case of Gaza, *International Journal of Social Sciences Research and Development (IJSSRD)*, 6(1), pp. 200-215.
- [7] Buheji, M (2024e) How is Gaza Inspiring Gen-Z and Changing Their Mindsets? *International Journal of Social Sciences Research and Development*, 6(1), pp. 1-22.
- [8] Buheji, M (2024f) Overcoming Feelings of Betrayal and Let Down - Extending Shows of Resilience in Gaza. *International Journal of Management (IJM)*, 15(1), 2024, 174-187.
- [9] Buheji, M (2023) Redefining the Meaning of Hardiness- Gaza Lab, *International Journal of Management (IJM)*, 14(7), pp. 77-95.
- [10] Buheji, M (2021) Influence of Multidisciplinary Thinking Approaches in Poverty Elimination – Case of Afghanistan, *International Journal of Management (IJM)*, 12(9), 2021, pp. 19-31.
- [11] Buheji, M (2016) *Handbook of Inspiration Economy*. Bookboon, London, UK.
- [12] Buheji, M and Ahmed, D (2024) Insights from Testing Empathy Levels Towards Gaza – A Profound Scale, *International Journal of Management (IJM)*, 15(2), pp. 27-48.

- [13] Buheji, M and Ahmed, D (2023) Keeping the Boycott Momentum- from ‘WAR on GAZA’ Till ‘Free-Palestine’, *International Journal of Management (IJM)*, 14(7), pp. 205-229.
- [14] Buheji, M; Al-Muhannadi, K (2023) Mitigating Risks of Environmental Impacts on Gaza - Review of Precautions & Solutions post (2023 War), *International Journal of Advanced Research in Engineering and Technology*, 14(7), pp. 15-47.
- [15] Buheji, M; BenAmer, M; Hasan, A (2024a) The Sacrifice, How Pro-Palestine Protests Students are Sacrificing to Change the World? *Gradiva*, 63:(5), pp. 83-104.
- [16] Buheji, M and Buheji, B (2024) Mitigating Risks of Slow Children Development Due to War on Gaza 2023, *International Journal of Psychology and Behavioral Sciences*, 14(1): 11-21
- [17] Buheji, M and Khunji, A (2023) Rehabilitating Gaza’s Wellbeing Through Storytelling (During & After War 2023), *International Journal of Advanced Research in Social Sciences and Humanities (IJARSSH)*, 7 (1), 2023, pp. 9–21.
- [18] Buheji, M; Mushimiyimana, E and Ahmed, D (2024b) Empathic Engagement with Gaza: Dynamics, Impact, and Prospects, *International Journal of Management (IJM)*, 15(1), pp. 132-156.
- [19] Buheji, M and Mushimiyimana, E (2024b) (GAZA 2024) Revising The ‘Reasons to Live’ An Assessment of Current Scenarios & Foresighted Future, *International Journal of Management (IJM)*, 15(1), 2024, pp. 209-229.
- [20] Buheji, M and Mushimiyimana, E (2023a) “Gaza” – Towards an Agile Resilience, *International Journal of Management (IJM)*, 14(7), pp. 120- 136.
- [21] Buheji, M and Mushimiyimana, E (2023b) Raising Gaza Survival Capacity as Per Violence Experienced, Lesson from Best War Survival Stories in Recent History, *International Journal of Advanced Research in Social Sciences and Humanities (IJARSSH)*, 7 (1), 2023, pp. 22–48.
- [22] Buheji, M; Hamza, J (2024) Branding Resilience: Shaping Gaza’s Global Identity through Narrative, Solidarity, and Advocacy, *International Journal of Advanced and Multidisciplinary Social Science*, 2024; 9(1): 1-10.
- [23] Buheji, M and Hasan, A (2024a) Beyond Famine and Chaos – Case of Gaza, *International Journal of Management (IJM)*, 15(2), pp. 1-26.
- [24] Buheji, M and Hasan, A (2024b) Capitalising on the ‘Social Capital’ That Would Accelerate the Collective Wealth of Gaza, *International Journal of Social Sciences Research and Development (IJSSRD)*, 6(1), pp. 134-152.
- [25] Buheji, M and Hasan, A (2024a) Can Celebrities be Neutral About Gaza? *International Journal of Management (IJM)*, 15(3), 2024, pp. 171-191.
- [26] Buheji, M and Hasan, A (2024b) Challenging Injustice - Stretching the ‘Academic Boycott’ After War on Gaza 2023, *Gradiva*, Vol (63):5.
- [27] Buheji, M and Hasan, A (2024c) Echoes of Wake-Up-Realising the Impact of The Seeds of Student Pro-Palestine Protests, *International Journal of Management (IJM)*, 15(3), pp. 56-86.
- [28] Buheji, M and Hasan, A (2024d) Spain's Empathy for Gaza as A Model for The World and the Communities Mechanism, *International Journal of Management (IJM)*, 15(3), pp. 1-15.

- [29] Buheji, M and Hasan, A (2024e) The Beginning of The End A Comparison Between the Apartheid (South Africa Vs. Israeli Occupation), International Journal of Management (IJM), 15(1), 2024, pp. 241-264.
- [30] Hasan, A (2024) Education Resilience Under the Occupation- Case of Palestine, International Journal of Inspiration, Resilience & Youth Economy, 8(1): p. 33-45.
- [31] Hasan, A and Buheji, M (2024) A World Losing Its Legitimacy - Gaza from Collective Punish till Ethnic Cleansing & Genocide, International Journal of Management (IJM), 15(1), 2024, pp. 188-209.
- [32] Hassoun A, Al-Muhannadi K, Hassan HF, Hamad A, Khwaldia K, Buheji M and Al Jawaldeh A (2024) From acute food insecurity to famine: how the 2023/2024 war on Gaza has dramatically set back sustainable development goal 2 to end hunger. Front. Sustain. Food Syst. 8:1402150.
- [33] Hill, L (1994) Exercising Influence, Harvard Business Review
- [34] Phusavat, K and Buheji, M (2024) Mapping Informal Learning for Displaced Learners during the War on Gaza 2023- Application of Situated Cognition, International Journal of Learning and Development, Vol. 14, No. 1, pp. 1-16.
- [35] Shorrab, A; Nassef, M; Subhi, A; Giwa, B; Buheji, M (2024) Health in the Crossfire - Analyzing and Mitigating the Multifaceted Health Risks of the 2023 War on Gaza, Public Health Research, 14(1): 1-11.

Citation: Mohamed Buheji, ‘Influencing Without Power’ for A Good Cause - The Experience of Gaza Resilience Lab, International Journal of Social Sciences Research and Development (IJSSRD), 6(2), 2024, pp. 1-12.

Abstract Link

https://iaeme.com/Home/article_id/IJSSRD_06_02_001

Article Link:

https://iaeme.com/MasterAdmin/Journal_uploads/IJSSRD/VOLUME_6_ISSUE_2/IJSSRD_06_02_001.pdf

Copyright: © 2024 Authors. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

This work is licensed under a **Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0)**.

 editor@iaeme.com